

FUTURE CARDIOLOGISTS' PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IMAGING SYSTEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13144448>

Abstract. Professional competence is especially important for students of medical higher education institutions. In the treatment of these features in students, in combination with the absorption of knowledge, skills and qualifications, especially in the course of medicine, competencies should also be formed in them. Competence is the ability to apply the theoretical knowledge, skills and qualifications acquired by a student in a particular discipline in practice, using them to solve practical and theoretical issues encountered in the process of work. When a person diligently, lovingly approaches his work, training, no matter what profession he has, he perfectly occupies his secret reserve, at the same time becomes self-aware, matures in this area.

Keywords: future doctors, medical institutions of higher education, students, professional competence, knowledge, skills and qualifications, integration, lesson.

Introduction. Currently, it is necessary to consider the ability to form a competence in students of the Institute of medicine as a direct main factor in the formation of mature specialists in the future. Indeed, the future is precisely in the hands of future doctors, students who are being brought up in the present. We cannot lead future doctors to the current world of modern medicine without modern innovative techniques. Among students of medical higher education institutions, the professional competence is considered especially important. It is necessary that future doctors be able to keep close relatives ready even for emergency situations, until they can measure normal blood pressure or perform inextinguishable procedures.

Experienced doctors advise a lot to go “you should always be responsible and alert at a time outside work, on weekends even when you go on a trip”. The modern educational process cannot be imagined without the search for new, more effective technologies that will help develop the professional and creative abilities of students. The science of Cardiology is considered the most important science that all should know, and not just future cardiologists. Because the most important organ of the human body is the heart. It is impossible to study any clinical science without knowing the structure of the human body.

But Cardiology is one of the most difficult subjects for all medical students. Therefore, quality training of this course is very important for the release of worthy specialists. At the present stage, the training of qualified specialists in any field of Medicine implies the use of innovative technologies. At the same time, the historical experience of teaching Cardiology shows that it is most acceptable to harmonize traditional approaches to the organization of the educational process with modern, innovative teaching methods.

Research Methodology. The subject “Cardiology”, which is transferred to 5-6 courses at Andijan State Medical Institute, forms the necessary professional competence for our future doctors-cardiologists. Especially our students who have chosen Cardiology, resuscitation and surgical sphere will have primary and necessary knowledge in the science of “Cardiology”.

Pulse detection in the arteries of the wrist, thigh and head, topography of the peripheral and central veins - all this is called competence, while the fact that our students are able to apply them

as a source of basic knowledge in the future of becoming mature specialists. And the modern innovative approach is carried out using 3D models, millions in the body that are suitable for the requirements of the new time, traditional methods (discussion, rotation, weak hoop, etc.).

Because the role of advanced pedagogical technologies in the formation of professional competencies in students in innovative education is incomparable in the development of students into a person with a broad worldview, who, during the course of the lesson, does not only listen or repeat what he has heard, but also acts in deep observation, expresses his independent opinion, works in cooperation with others.

Taking classes using interactive methods ensures independent acquisition of scientific and theoretical knowledge in students, formation of knowledge and skills, qualifications and, on this basis, the formation and activity of students' scientific worldview, training in free thinking, identification and realization of their creative abilities, formation of teacher-student cooperation and finally achieving a guaranteed final result. In interactive methods, the teacher is engaged in creating an environment for the student to receive independent and excellent knowledge, directing him to master the basics of science, arousing interest, affection.

Process criterion in the methodological training of the future medical teacher: communicative skills –the skill of organizing pedagogical communication with students in the educational process, the ability to build relationships with the pedagogical purpose, the ability to analyze the levels of intelligibility of the expression of assignments in various medical teaching datures for future medical teachers, skills aimed at ensuring the Integrative activities of future medical teachers; information skills - the ability to master new knowledge through information and communication technologies, the ability to choose effective technologies in the educational process and apply innovative technologies to the educational process are reflected.

In preparing a medical profession for teaching students based on professional-pedagogical competence, it focuses on: to form a single basis for the formation of scientific concepts in various fields of knowledge, to arm students in medicine with competencies such as stimulating, cognitive, didactic, information-communicative, striving for medical professional creativity and growth, methodological medical knowledge, medical research, diantological approach.

Conclusion. The implementation of an approach based on professional competence in education is the acquisition of the knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for the implementation of professional activity by a professional competence - specialist associated with the concepts of "competence", "professional competence" and their high degree of application in practice.

In place of the conclusion, it is worth mentioning that it is important to gain continuing education, practice and experience so that future doctors have these competencies. This will help them succeed in their professional activities and provide patients with high-quality medical care.

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